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Role and Challenges of Forensic Science in Crime Scene Investigation

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Abstract

Modern criminal investigations depend heavily on forensic science by offering empirical data to help law enforcement organizations and the courts. The use of forensic methods, such DNA analysis, in the investigation digital forensics, ballistics, fingerprinting, and analysis have completely changed the manner in which crimes are investigated and prosecuted. In India, Forensic science has been essential in deciphering complicated crimes cases, but issues like aging infrastructure and a lack of a lack of trained forensic professionals, delays in forensic analysis, and insufficient Law enforcement officers are more conscious of forensic uses prevent it from reaching its full potential. The importance of forensics is discussed in this article explores major challenges encountered in the use of science in criminal investigations India, and recommends improvements to increase its efficiency.

Keywords Forensic Science, Crime Scene, Investigation, Evidence, Criminal Justice.

Introduction

Forensic science is a multidisciplinary field that makes use of scientific approaches has become increasingly important in the criminal justice system as a means of looking into and solving crimes all over the world. It offers crucial assistance in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of evidence that can aid in determining facts, identifying suspects, and bringing criminals to justice. In conclusion, Forensic science has also been identified as a vital component of the Indian environment. The criminal justice system, which is used in investigations and court procedures.

Objective of study

To find out challenges while investigation of crime scene.

Review of Literature

Bansal S, Nayak SS, Dave I. (2025) The Role of Forensic Science and Digital Technology in enhancing Investigation Efficacy: An Analytical Study- Law enforcement organizations have changed their strategies and significantly improved their capacity to solve crimes thanks to the integration of technology into criminal investigations. This study explores the significant impact that advancements in forensic science and digital technology have on criminal investigations by looking at their evolution and how they are utilized in current practice. Because surveillance technologies, digital forensics, and DNA analysis have all transformed the way evidence is collected and evaluated, their application is a crucial subject for discussion. The issues and limitations that these technological advancements have caused are also covered in this article, such as privacy ethics, dependability issues, and the potential for digital injustices.

Bilal J, Riaz Z, Sharif M. (2025) Preservation of Crime Scene: An Analysis of Guidelines, Legal Framework and Judicial Interpretation. - In order to ensure justice in legal procedures, it is imperative that the crime scene be protected. Every nation's criminal court demand that the charges against the accused be proven beyond a reasonable doubt. Events that occurred at the crime site are analysed and reconstructed with the help of criminal justice. Although the police officers did not witness these

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incidents, forensic specialists and crime scene investigators use certain elements to piece together the pieces of evidence and reconstruct a story.

Tiwari A, Kusum S. (2024) Role of Forensic Criminology in Access to Justice—A Critical Analysis- Forensic science originated during the Roman Empire as an applied discipline of science in civil and criminal laws, which were enforced by courts and police. The establishment of Central and State Forensic Science Laboratories, the Bureau of Police Research and Development, and teaching Departments of Forensic Science in several universities has led to the slow but steady growth of forensic science education, training, research, and development in India.

Nilendu D. (2024) Enhancing forensic education: exploring the importance and implementation of evidence-based education system.- It is becoming more and more necessary to have forensic science graduates with expertise in the most recent best practices, not just nationally but also globally. Incidents and trends highlight the critical need for evidence-based instruction in forensic science to ensure that future practitioners are equipped to handle complicated crime scenarios and challenges. Forensic education must remain current and responsive to the changing demands of the industry through Body Collaboration between academics and real-world practitioners. The collaboration between the former "National Institute of Criminology and Forensic Science (NICFS)" and the "Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI)" in India provides a clear example of how well they worked together. This partnership has greatly improved forensic education in India by closing the gap between theoretical understanding and real-world application through collaborative projects.

Banerji B, Kumar KV, Kaur A. Review of forensic science in India:-

Pokhariyal P, Dubey D. (2023) The Imperative of Forensic Justice in Modern Legal Systems: A Comprehensive Analysis.- Forensic justice, an essential cornerstone of modern jurisprudence, The clarion call for precise policy delineations in order to achieve its goals is beckoned by the clarion call a wide range of possibilities. This chapter begins a methodical examining the boundaries of forensic justice and methodically exposing its subtle complexities and far-reaching consequences.

Pandey A. (2023) The Impact of Forensic evidence on the Criminal Justice system in India: An examination of opportunities, challenges, and future directions- Criminal trials and investigations have benefited greatly from the use of forensic evidence attracting attention in recent years due to the growing dependence on such evidence in legal proceedings. Forensics there is potential for evidence to provide considerable benefits in the criminal justice system, such as the following: improving the evidence's quality, aiding in the identification of culprits, and exonerating the blameless. However, forensic evidence also poses a variety of challenges, such as technical ones. obstacles in the legal, institutional, and cultural spheres. This article analyses the consequences of forensic India's criminal justice system, looking at opportunities, challenges, and the future, is the subject of this proof directions.

Kothari P. (2023) Exploring the Role of Forensic Science in Indian Criminal Justice System- There are several scientific fields covered by forensic science, such as digital forensics, ballistics, toxicology, fingerprint analysis, and DNA analysis. These disciplines are essential for evidence collecting, analysing, and presenting it in court, as well as for crime scene investigation. The significance of forensic science in the Indian "Criminal Justice System" (CJS) has become increasingly apparent in recent years. It is essential to the CJS since it offers scientific data that helps in the investigation and adjudication of criminal cases. The Indian criminal justice system's use of forensic science is fraught with difficulties that have an impact on the calibre and dependability of forensic data. These challenges include the lack of clear guidelines for the gathering, preservation, and analysis of forensic evidence, the lack of complete forensic training programs for law enforcement officers, the limited standardization and accreditation of forensic laboratories, and the out-of-date forensic infrastructure. These problems may contribute to the mishandling of evidence, contamination, and untrustworthy results, all of which might have a negative impact on the conclusion of criminal cases and result in miscarriages of justice. Overcoming these challenges can improve the quality and trustworthiness of forensic evidence, fortify the Indian criminal justice system, and guarantee that justice is administered fairly and reliably.

Kathane P, Singh A, Gaur JR, Krishan K. (2021) The development, status and future of forensics in India. - India has established several forensic facilities for the prompt resolution of criminal cases via scientific inquiry conducted both in the field and in the labs. However, the infrastructure established has not kept up with the growing caseload of criminal cases. In order to modernize forensics in India, ongoing attempts are being made to develop additional infrastructure in the workforce, equipment, science, and technology, but there is still a greater need for forensics capacity building in India. The article examines the current situation, challenges, academic and research endeavors, future avenues, and needs of forensics in India.

Mack S, Chatterjee I. Role of forensic evidence in criminal justice delivery system in India.- The use of the physical and natural sciences to examine civil or criminal cases falls under the purview of forensic science. It is employed for a variety of purposes, including analyzing criminal offenses like rape, murder, and drug trafficking, as well as civil matters like intentionally destroying the environment. It involves utilizing contemporary methods like DNA testing, fingerprint analysis, and drug testing to ascertain the details of the crime and the offender. According to the Indian Evidence Act (IEA) of 1872, the research identifies that evidence has been divided into several categories, including Oral Evidence, Documentary Evidence, Primary evidence, and Judicial Evidence, all of which are crucial to the investigative process. According to the study, forensic investigations are very helpful because they monitor the effects of the illegal drugs and identify the residues by recreating the crime scene. Additionally, forensic investigations are useful in finding the victim and learning about the causes and behaviour of the crime.

Main Text

However, forensic science's significance is acknowledged, but there are difficulties which has an impact on its efficiency and reliability in the Indian judicial system. These difficulties include concerns regarding infrastructure, training, standardization, and the admissibility of forensic evidence in court. The changing character of offenses and Forensic science in India faces new challenges due to technological advancements. The absence of insufficient training and resources for forensic professionals, as well as standardized procedures and recommendations, In addition, the caliber and dependability of forensic might be impacted by shortcomings in the forensic infrastructure data that might result in unjust acquittals or convictions. Thus, a thorough study is urgently needed to evaluate the existing situation. Identify issues with the current state of forensic science in the Indian criminal justice system, and offer recommendations proposals for its improvement based on evidence. The gaps may be filled by this study as well as restrictions in Indian forensic science practice, improve the caliber and reliability of forensic evidence, and make sure the criminal justice system is fair and trustworthy upholding the ideals of justice and due process.

The Function of Forensic Science in Criminal Investigations- Forensic science covers a wide range of scientific fields that aid in criminal investigations, such as: forensic anthropology, digital forensics, ballistics, toxicology, serology, and DNA fingerprinting. Forensics Science is the use of scientific ideas and methods to look into crimes and legal issues concerns. It entails gathering, maintaining, and analyzing physical evidence to determine the truth and help with legal procedures. "Forensic" is derived from the Latin forensis, which means "of or." emphasizing its function in providing evidence in courts of law, before the forum. Forensic science develops over time has developed into a multidisciplinary field that includes forensic biology and other related subfields toxicology, digital forensics, forensic chemistry, and criminal profiling.

Forensic science is the fascinating discipline that uses science to solve the mysteries of crime. An essential component of the Indian Criminal Justice System (CJS) is now investigation. A vast range of scientific methods and methodologies are covered by this interdisciplinary subject. which help with the gathering, preservation, study, and presentation of data in courts of law. Forensic science is essential to the process, from DNA profiling to fingerprint analysis. investigation and prosecution of crimes in India, revealing the truth in the most complicated situations. It has grown into a potent instrument for locating offenders, connecting them to the crime scene, and providing proof in judicial proceedings.

Forensic science encompasses a wide range of fields, not only criminal investigations. One of its main One of the most common applications of forensic science is crime scene investigation, where forensic specialists examine fingerprints, DNA samples, and other evidence bloodstains, ballistic evidence, and other physical traces left at a crime scene. This data supports the rule of law. To identify suspects, reconstruct events, and support witness testimony, law enforcement authorities take action. DNA The use of profiling has transformed criminal investigations by making it possible to identify criminals with great precision people according to their genetic traits. One of the oldest forensic methods, fingerprint analysis, is still used today to serve as a key means of connecting perpetrators to crime scenes.

Forensic toxicology, which is concerned with the discovery and the study of medications, toxins, and other compounds found in biological specimens. In cases of drug misuse, poisoning, and establishing the reason for death during autopsy, this branch is very crucial. In forensics Anthropology studies skeletal remains to identify victims and analyze injuries, which helps. historical studies and mass disaster investigations. The nascent discipline of forensic psychology also aids. analyzing psychological states, comprehending offenders' conduct, and utilizing criminal profiling.

Due to the increase in complicated crimes like cybercrime, there is a growing need for forensic science in India organized criminal conduct and white-collar offenses. Forensic science has been established by the government laboratories at the national and state levels, such as the Central Forensic Science Laboratory (CFSL) and the State Forensic Science Laboratories (SFSLs) to support investigations. Forensic science is still undervalued despite its significance. encounters difficulties such as a lack of qualified professionals, delays in forensic reports, and restrictions in advancements in technology. integrating, training staff, and enhancing forensic infrastructure bringing forensic training into law enforcement is a crucial step in improving the function of forensic science in the judicial system.

Among the main contributions of forensic science to criminal investigations are:
Identifying Criminals and Victims-The capacity to identify victims and offenders is one of the most important contributions of forensic science using a scientific approach.

1. DNA Fingerprinting: One of the most dependable forensic methods for identifying individuals is DNA profiling. Identifying victims and suspects. DNA is used in cases of murder, rape, and missing people. Identities may be determined with great accuracy with the use of evidence. In the Nirbhaya case, for instance, forensics The perpetrators were identified through DNA analysis.
2. Facial and Fingerprint Recognition: Automated Fingerprint Identification Systems (AFIS) give police the ability to compare fingerprints discovered at crime scenes with national databases. Facial To identify suspects, forensic investigations are also integrating recognition technology based on video from CCTV.
3. Reconstruction of the Crime Scene-By analyzing physical evidence, forensic science aids law enforcement organizations in re-creating crime scenes.
4. Bloodstain Pattern Analysis: By examining blood spatter, one can ascertain the victim's location, the kind of assault and the weapon employed.
5. Firearms and Ballistics Analysis: The firing of a bullet can be determined using forensic ballistics by identifying individuals to crimes involving guns through the use of a particular weapon.
6. Forensic Toxicology: In cases of alcohol-related offenses, drug overdoses, or poisonings, forensic toxicology is used Blood, urine, and tissue specimens are examined by forensic toxicologists for the presence of harmful chemicals.
7. Improving the Judiciary- In legal proceedings, forensic evidence is an essential component because of its reliability.
8. Forensic evidence is used by courts to support the statements made by witnesses and to ascertain information beyond that a fair doubt.
9. Forensic pathology reports and DNA evidence are essential for ensuring fair trials and preventing wrongfull verdicts.
10. Cybercrime Investigations Using Digital Forensics. Due to the increase in cybercrime, digital forensics has established itself as a vital component of forensic science.
11. Digital forensic specialists trace cybercriminals, retrieve erased data, and examine electronic devices activities. Digital forensics offers vital evidence in incidents of cyber fraud, identity theft, and hacking by tracking IP addresses and data that is encrypted.

Challenges in Crime Scene Investigation-

1. One of the major issues in the field of forensic science is the absence of standardization.
2. The absence of uniform methods and procedures in India.³⁵ The absence of consistency in inconsistencies and mistakes in the evidence may result from its collection, preservation, and analysis.
3. Forensic evaluation procedure, which calls into question the validity of the findings.
4. Restricted Resources and Infrastructure: Forensic facilities in India frequently run into problems of insufficient infrastructure, obsolete technology, and a lack of qualified workforce.
5. This may impede the prompt and precise examination of evidence, leading to delays in investigations as well as legal proceedings.
6. Ensuring the quality and reliability of forensic procedures through accreditation and quality control
7. Evidence is essential to the criminal justice system. Nevertheless, there are a lot of forensic labs in India.
8. Due to the absence of quality control procedures and accreditation, there are worries about the correctness and forensic results' integrity.
9. Case Backlog: There is a constant backlog of cases waiting for forensic evaluation problem with the Indian criminal justice system. Due to the forensics' restricted capacity evidence frequently remains unanalyzed for in laboratories and the growing number of cases. which can cause delays in trials and investigations.

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10. The restricted public awareness and education are further difficulties. This might lead to inappropriate evidence collection, which is why it is crucial to educate the Indian public, legal community, and law enforcement agencies about the value of forensic science.
11. Evidence mishandling and the ineffective use of forensic methods in trials and investigations.

Conclusion

Worldwide, forensic science has been instrumental in criminal investigations and justice systems. To improve the precision and dependability of criminal investigations. Despite the extraordinary advances made in forensic science, developing nations continue to struggle with technology, training, and other issues in developed countries accessibility.

Forensic science in developing nations faces a number of obstacles, such as a lack of infrastructure, restricted funding and a scarcity of skilled workers. In several nations in South Asia and Africa, Law enforcement agencies are still having trouble integrating modern forensic techniques, which are constantly changing. Forensic methods in their legal systems. But efforts are being made to enhance forensic science. abilities via technology transfers, training programs, and international partnerships. The UN Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) and INTERPOL are two examples of organizations that have actively participated in improving forensic science worldwide.

In general, forensic science has revolutionized criminal investigations all across the world by providing greater precision, fair, scientific, and judicial proceedings. As the more developed nations keep pushing the envelope developing countries must concentrate on extending their use of big data, automation, and artificial intelligence in forensic analysis. Forensic resources to close the gap and improve the administration of justice.

Forensic science is a valuable instrument in criminal investigations, performing a vital function in upholding justice but there are difficulties, like the requirement for legal reforms, case backlogs, and insufficient infrastructure impede its efficacy in India. Modernizing forensic labs, investing in forensic training, and India can improve its criminal justice system by incorporating AI-driven technologies. Future initiatives should prioritize improving forensic science literacy among the general public and in the legal community, as well as promoting fair trials and enhancing the reliability of forensic evidence.

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